

HEREDITARY

HetERogeneous sEmantic Data integration for the guT-bRain interplaY

Deliverable 3.11

Pilot of the genomics data science ontology interconversion

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable, *D3.11 – Pilot of the Genomics Data Science Ontology Interconversion*, presents an initial demonstration of semantic interoperability between genomic and clinical data within the *HEREDITARY* project. *HEREDITARY* seeks to enable federated, privacy-preserving machine learning across diverse datasets for neurodegenerative and neurodevelopmental conditions, a goal that requires harmonized data structures and FAIR-compliant mechanisms for data discovery.

The pilot integrates two complementary efforts. First, a Beacon v2 instance was deployed on a controlled-access local server and populated with 200 whole-genome sequences from the University of Turin (UNITO) Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS) cohort, demonstrating the feasibility of standardized variant-level data discovery within the project. Second, a manual semantic harmonization was carried out between the AnswerALS clinical dictionary, which contains 880 variables, and the PARALS dictionary used by UNITO for their ALS cohort. This work identified 18 exact or semantically aligned correspondences and provides an initial bridge to the *HEREDITARY* Ontology (HERO). A parallel mapping between PARALS and the Beacon v2 schema further supports future integration of phenotypic metadata into the Beacon environment.

Together, these developments constitute the first step toward an ontology-driven, interoperable data ecosystem capable of supporting federated analytics across ALS cohorts. It establishes the technical and methodological foundation for the full demonstrator to be delivered next year.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
ALS	Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis
API	Application Programming Interface
B2PI	Beacon v2 Production Implementation (EGA Beacon v2 API Implementation Toolkit)
BFF	Beacon-Friendly Format
CRG	Centre for Genomic Regulation
EGA	European Genome-phenome Archive
ELIXIR	European Life-Science Infrastructure for Biological Information
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
HGVS	Human Genome Variation Society (nomenclature for describing genetic variants)
HPC4AI	High-Performance Computing for Artificial Intelligence (UNITO infrastructure)
INDEL	Insertion–Deletion variant
PARALS	Piemonte and Valle d’Aosta Register for Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis
SNP	Single Nucleotide Polymorphism
UNITO	University of Turin
VCF	Variant Call Format
WGS	Whole Genome Sequencing

1 Context and motivation

The HEREDITARY project aims to enable federated learning across multimodal biomedical data to advance research in neurodegenerative diseases, while ensuring data sovereignty, privacy, and FAIR compliance. Achieving this objective requires that heterogeneous datasets—collected under different protocols and stored in distinct infrastructures—can be made semantically interoperable and computationally harmonized.

Within this framework, the present deliverable, *Pilot of the Genomics Data Science Ontology Interconversion (D3.11)*, focuses on establishing interoperability between two independent cohorts of patients with Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS): one collected at the University of Turin (UNITO), comprising approximately 1300 subjects with Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) data, and another from the AnswerALS initiative (Baxi et al. 2022). The UNITO dataset is collected using the PARALS clinical registry (Chiò et al. 2017), a long-standing epidemiological register for ALS in the Piemonte and Valle d’Aosta regions. The dataset’s demographic and clinical data is described in (Chio et al. 2025). Although these datasets originate from different sources and use different clinical dictionaries, they share a common disease focus, making them a suitable test case for ontology-based harmonization and cross-cohort interoperability.

A key component of this pilot relies on the GA4GH Beacon protocol (Rambla et al. 2022), an international standard for federated genomic data discovery. Beacon enables institutions to make genomic datasets discoverable in a controlled, privacy-preserving manner through a simple query interface, making it an essential tool for FAIR genomic data sharing in distributed environments.

Beacon schema primarily allows sharing of genomic and phenoclinical data while giving the Beacon owners a full control over the data accessibility. Beacon can return individual-level data under appropriate access conditions (controlled access), or alternatively return high-level information on the existence of the variation and/or aggregated metrics, such as allele counts or frequencies. The Beacon instances are hosted locally by the data custodians and can be incorporated into a Beacon network for a secure federated discovery across multiple institutions or countries. This architecture supports interoperability and enables researchers to identify datasets of interest while preserving participant confidentiality.

The Centre for Genomic Regulation (CRG) is a key institution in the Beacon ecosystem and is involved in both expansion of the GA4GH Beacon specification, as well as development of relevant technical solutions. CRG developed and maintained the [Beacon v2 Production Implementation \(B2PI\)](#), an out-of-the-box Beacon deployment toolkit that facilitates institutions to stand up their own instances. B2PI, which is also the solution of this pilot, is the main implementation toolkit adopted by several European projects, including Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) aiming to build a European genomic data sharing infrastructure. Additionally, CRG is hosting two international Beacon networks – [Global Beacon Atlas](#) and [ELIXIR Beacon Network](#) - that are gathering individual Beacon instances and/or Beacon Networks at global or European level, respectively, for improved data visibility and findability. Rather than storing genomic data centrally, the network aggregates metadata endpoints from participating Beacons, enabling users to broadcast a single query across thousands of datasets while each institution retains

sovereignty over its data. This demonstrates how Beacon supports scalable, privacy-preserving, and FAIR-aligned genomic discovery across distributed infrastructures.

Genomic datasets within the HEREDITARY project are highly sensitive and remain under strict custodianship. Hence, the present pilot constitutes an ideal test case for implementing data FAIRification strategies across the project. By *beaconizing* the UNITO genomic data locally—keeping all VCF files within the institution’s-controlled infrastructure—the team demonstrated how discoverability can be enabled without compromising data sovereignty.

While the genomic component of the UNITO cohort was already in a format suitable for immediate *beaconization*, the associated clinical data required additional preparation. To position the PARALS registry used for data collection, for future integration into Beacon, this deliverable includes an initial mapping between PARALS variables and the Beacon v2 data model. This exercise identifies how PARALS clinical concepts—such as demographic descriptors, diagnostic information, exposures, biosample attributes, and clinical measurements—correspond to the entities defined in the Beacon specification. Establishing this semantic alignment provides the foundational bridge needed to eventually link the UNITO cohort phenotypic information with the Beaconized genomic data.

In summary, this deliverable presents a first pilot toward these goals, demonstrating a two-part interoperability effort:

1. **Genomic Beaconization Pilot** – deployment of a Beacon v2 instance for a subset of the UNITO ALS cohort, containing whole genome sequencing (WGS) data from over 1300 patients, of which 200 genomes were beaconized for this pilot.
2. **Clinical Data Harmonization Pilot** – mapping and interconversion between the AnswerALS clinical dictionary (880 fields) and the PARALS dictionary (~100 fields), as well as a complementary mapping between PARALS variables and the Beacon v2 model to support future integration of phenotypic information.

Together, these components form the first prototype of the project’s wider goal: an integrated, ontology-driven ecosystem for interoperable genomic and clinical datasets, suitable for federated learning and cross-cohort discovery.

2 Methodology

2.1 Beaconizing of the UNITO ALS cohort

The genomic component of the UNITO ALS cohort was *beaconized* at UNITO as part of this pilot to enable privacy-preserving variant-level discovery through the GA4GH Beacon v2 protocol. This work constitutes the first operational step toward beaconizing the full UNITO dataset—including both genomic and phenotypic layers—in subsequent HEREDITARY milestones.

2.1.1 Dataset and scope of the pilot

The source dataset comprises whole genome sequencing (WGS) data for more than 1300 individuals enrolled in the UNITO cohort. For the purposes of Deliverable D3.11, a subset of 200 fully consented subjects was processed and beaconized. In this pilot, only genomic variant data were included; no clinical or phenotypic metadata were ingested.

2.1.2 Beaconization workflow

Beaconization followed the GA4GH Beacon v2 specification and was implemented using the **EGA Beacon v2 API Implementation Toolkit (B2PI)**, which provides a standardized framework for transforming raw genomic variant files into Beacon-compatible data structures and endpoints.

(a) Input data preparation

The input consisted exclusively of **VCF files** produced from the WGS pipeline of the UNITO cohort. During preprocessing:

- Each variant line was interpreted according to GA4GH conventions (CHROM, POS, REF, ALT, FILTER, INFO).
- Indels were **left-aligned** and represented in **minimal canonical form**.
- Multi-allelic variants were **split** into separate entries to ensure compatibility with Beacon's variant representation requirements.

(b) Transformation to Beacon-Friendly Format

Following normalization, the VCF files were converted into the Beacon-Friendly Format (BFF), an optimized internal representation used by the B2PI toolkit to structure variant information for efficient querying. The resulting BFF records were stored in the Beacon backend MongoDB and indexes were created manually. These indexes enable performant chromosome-position lookups and variant-based queries.

2.1.3 Deployment and exposure of Beacon endpoints

The resulting Beacon instance was deployed on a **local, controlled-access server** through the local HPC4AI team (<https://hpc4ai.unito.it/>). In the current pilot configuration, there is only a base path through the server's IP, which works exclusively with the Beacon API <http://130.192.100.173/api/>. From this base path, the Beacon endpoints can be accessed, as described in the online Beacon documentation (http://130.192.100.173/api/g_variants). This instance exposes:

- **Dataset metadata endpoints** (descriptions, identifiers, reference genome, etc.)

- **Variation-level query endpoints**, enabling structured queries such as “Does any sample in this dataset contain a given variant?”

No user interface is provided locally, as long-term integration is planned with the **ELIXIR Beacon Network**.

2.2 Semantic Mapping Methodology (AnswerALS ↔ PARALS ↔ Beacon-v2)

The mappings performed in this pilot—between the AnswerALS clinical dictionary and the PARALS dictionary, and between the GA4GH Beacon v2 data model and PARALS—were essential steps toward achieving semantic interoperability between heterogeneous ALS datasets. Although these resources capture overlapping aspects of ALS patient information, they use different naming conventions, structures, and levels of detail. Establishing explicit correspondences between their fields ensures that concepts referring to the same underlying clinical meaning can be consistently aligned.

The primary purpose of both mappings is to enable integrated data discovery, harmonized analysis, and future federated learning within the HEREDITARY project. By identifying which clinical concepts are shared across datasets—such as demographics, lifestyle exposures, biosample characteristics, diagnostic information, disease progression scores, and comorbidities—these mappings provide the conceptual and technical foundation for cross-cohort comparisons and ontology-driven harmonization.

2.2.1 Mapping Procedure to AnswerALS clinical dictionary

The mapping process followed a structured multi-step workflow:

1. Dictionary extraction

AnswerALS clinical data dictionary was downloaded from their [website](#).

2. Initial semantic comparison

Each AnswerALS variable was systematically reviewed by a clinical research expert at the University of Turin, against all PARALS variables, with attention to the clinical meaning, data collection context, and intended use of each field to determine whether they represented equivalent or related concepts. Variables judged to be contextually similar were aligned within the same row of a shared spreadsheet, forming the preliminary basis for the harmonisation table.

3. Mapping rules

Mapped fields were examined for the two sub-fields: Field-Name and Value. Two new columns were created with the titles: Field-match-type indicating the field name matching category, and value-match-type indicating the value matching category. Matching categories were set as follows:

- (a) Exact: when the text in the field is an exact match.
- (b) Semantic: when the match is semantic.
- (c) Missing: when the field did not map.
- (d) No-value; when the field-name is mapped but the value is missing from either dictionary.

2.2.2 Mapping procedure to Beacon v2 model

Since the Beacon model is intentionally minimal, designed to support *genomic data discovery* rather than clinical characterisation, only a small subset of PARALS fields could be meaningfully mapped to Beacon entities. Mapping was performed by a Beacon model expert at the CRG team. The beacon model organises information into a small set of structured entities—**Individuals**, **Biosamples**, **Genomic Variations**, **Analyses**, and **Datasets**. The mapped fields corresponded primarily to **Individuals** entity, including subject ID, sex, date of birth, diseases including comorbidities, exposure (e.g. smoking), interventions and procedures (e.g. feeding tube admission), measures (e.g. ALS scale measures and blood tests). Variables judged to be contextually similar were aligned within the same row of a shared spreadsheet.

2.2.3 Final harmonization tables

Two mapping artefacts were produced: **AnswerALS** ↔ **PARALS mapping table** and **PARALS** ↔ **Beacon v2 mapping table** and can be found in **Annex 1** of this report.

3 Pilot Outcome

3.1 Beaconization Pilot Results

As part of the genomic *beaconization* of this pilot, a fully functional Beacon v2 server was deployed locally using B2PI. This instance supports variant-level queries across a subset of the UNITO ALS cohort that forms the foundation for the genomics interoperability demonstrated in this deliverable. Key characteristics of the deployment include:

- A **fully functional Beacon v2 server** deployed locally.
- Support of variant-level queries across a dataset of 200 WGS.
- Real patient data (under consent) was used.
- Controlled-access environment—no public exposure in the pilot.
- Interactions via API endpoints.

For *beaconizing* the dataset, conversion of the data was done using the Beacon v2 RI Tools plug in, inputting a VCF with the genomic variants and executing the script `docker exec -it ri-tools python genomicVariations_vcf.py`. A total set of 14,999,999 BSON records (compressed JSON inside a MongoDB instance), one per each variant.

The Beacon instance contains a single dataset representing genomic variation and therefore, currently only genomic-level queries are supported. These queries are in alignment with the GA4GH Beacon v2 specification (<https://docs.genomebeacons.org/variant-queries/>) and facilitated by the Beacon v2 Production Implementation instance. The following types of genomic queries are supported for which relevant data is available

- **Sequence queries**
- **Range queries**
- **Bracket queries**
- **Genomic allele queries**

For demonstration purposes, we are focusing on variants located at *SDHC* gene that can potentially cause Hereditary Pheochromocytoma/Paraganglioma Syndrome 3. Of note, unlike HGVS nomenclature which relies on 1-based genomic positions, Beacon queries are using 0-based positions, as defined by the GA4GH Beacon v2 specification.

Sequence queries

Sequence queries enable discovery of a specified sequence at a given genomic position. These queries are used to match short, precisely defined genomic variants such as SNPs and INDELS. Parameters for performing Sequence Queries:

- `referenceName`
- `start` (single value)
- `alternateBases`
- `referenceBases`
- `optional`
 - `variantType` OR `alternateBases` OR `aminoacidChange`

- variantMinLength
- variantMaxLength

This variant queried in this [example](#), is potentially linked to hereditary paragangliomas and pheochromocytomas. The simple lookup for the SNP can inform the user of the presence of the variant in the UNITO Beacon. This response is demonstrated in Figure 1 that captures the query for the variant NC_000001.11:g.161314419T>C on chromosome 1: 161314419 of the reference assembly GRCh38, and indicating the presence of a subject harboring the mutation.

```

{
  "meta": { ... }, // 6 items
  "responseSummary": { ... }, // 2 items
  "response": {
    "resultSets": [
      {
        "exists": true,
        "id": "Unito_ALS_genomics2",
        "results": [
          {
            "identifiers": {
              "genomicHGVSId": "NC_000001.11:g.161314419T>C"
            },
            "variantInternalId": "c2670ffb61b3d1f2c53f6cd5c90d944",
            "variation": {
              "alternateBases": "C",
              "location": {
                "type": "SequenceLocation",
                "sequence_id": "HGVSid:1:g.161314418T>C",
                "interval": {
                  "type": "SequenceInterval",
                  "start": {
                    "type": "Number",
                    "value": 161314418
                  },
                  "end": {
                    "type": "Number",
                    "value": 161314419
                  }
                }
              },
              "referenceBases": "T",
              "variantType": "SNP"
            }
          }
        ],
        "resultsCount": 1,
        "setType": "dataset"
      }
    ]
  }
}
    
```

Figure 1. Screenshot of a sequence query at the UNITO beacon API. The variant 1:161314419T>C was queried and a response was obtained indicating the presence of one variant in the cohort.

Range queries

Range queries facilitate querying variant with at least partial overlap of the sequence range specified by reference_name, start and end parameters. Parameters for performing a Range Query:

- referenceName
- start (single value)
- end (single value)
- optional
 - variantType OR alternateBases OR aminoacidChange
 - variantMinLength
 - variantMaxLength

For example, pathogenic variants in the *SDHC* gene can cause an autosomal dominant tumor-predisposition syndrome (SDH-associated paraganglioma/pheochromocytoma syndrome), which increases the risk of developing neuroendocrine tumors, most commonly paragangliomas (especially head and neck). Performing [a range query](#), specifying indels, enables the identification of such variants. In the UNITO ALS Beacon, 9 variants are found (Figure 2):

- NC_000001.11:g.161348487_161348493delinsG
- NC_000001.11:g.161348666_161348667delinsCAAAA
- NC_000001.11:g.161348667del
- NC_000001.11:g.161348666_161348667delinsCAAAAA
- NC_000001.11:g.161348666_161348667delinsCAA
- NC_000001.11:g.161348666_161348667delinsCAAA
- NC_000001.11:g.161348700del
- NC_000001.11:g.161348780del
- NC_000001.11:g.161348882_161348907delinsA

```

    {
      meta: {
        apiVersion: "v2.0.0",
        beaconId: "it.unito.cresla.beacon",
        receivedRequestSummary: {
          apiVersion: "Not provided",
          requestedSchemas: [],
          pagination: {
            skip: 0,
            limit: 10
          },
          requestedGranularity: "record",
          testMode: false,
          filters: [],
          requestParameters: {
            assemblyId: "GRCh38",
            referenceName: "1",
            start: [
              161348000
            ],
            end: [
              161349000
            ],
            variantType: "INDEL"
          },
          includeResultsetResponses: "HIT"
        },
        returnedGranularity: "record",
        returnedSchemas: [...], // 1 item
        testMode: false
      },
      responseSummary: {
        exists: true,
        numTotalResults: 9
      },
      response: {
        resultSets: [
          {
            exists: true,
            id: "Unito_ALS_genomics2",
            results: [...], // 9 items
            resultsCount: 9,
            setType: "dataset"
          }
        ]
      }
    }
  
```

Figure 2. Screenshot of a range query at the UNITO beacon API. Range query for INDELS in SDHC gene returned 9 variants. The details of the variants have been hidden in this screenshot but can be revealed by clicking on the arrow next to the results array.

Bracket Query

Bracket queries allow for performing searches using ranges of sequence positions, rather than specific start and end positions. The typical example here is the query for structural variants - particularly CNVs - affecting a genomic region but potentially differing in their exact start and/or end positions. Parameters for performing a bracket query are:

- referenceName
- start (min) and start (max) - i.e. 2 start parameters
- end (min) and end (max) - i.e. 2 end parameters
- variantType (optional)

In the following [example](#), the previously demonstrated range query is performed but using a bracket query, yielding similar results (Figure 3).

```

    "meta": {
      "apiVersion": "v2.0.0",
      "beaconId": "it.unito.cresla.beacon",
      "receivedRequestSummary": {
        "apiVersion": "Not provided",
        "requestedSchemas": [],
        "pagination": {
          "skip": 0,
          "limit": 10
        },
        "requestedGranularity": "record",
        "testMode": false,
        "filters": [],
        "requestParameters": {
          "referenceName": "1",
          "start": [
            161348000,
            161349000
          ],
          "end": [
            161348000,
            161349000
          ],
          "assemblyId": "GRCh38",
          "variantType": "INDEL"
        },
        "includeResultsetResponses": "HIT"
      },
      "returnedGranularity": "record",
      "returnedSchemas": [...], // 1 item
      "testMode": false
    },
    "responseSummary": {
      "exists": true,
      "numTotalResults": 9
    }
  
```

Figure 3. Screenshot of a bracket query at the UNITO beacon API. The bracket query on region 1:161348000 – 1:161349000 shows the same result generated with a Range query returning 9 indels.

Genomic Allele Queries

Genomic allele queries enable identification of a single variant (e.g. SNP) query by using their HGVS ID. This retrieves an identical result as for the Sequence Query demonstrated above (see [example](#)).

3.2 Clinical Data Harmonization Pilot Results

A core objective of the HEREDITARY project is to enable semantic interoperability across heterogeneous clinical and genomic datasets in support of federated analysis and FAIR data reuse. The clinical harmonization activities presented in this section provide a pilot evaluation of this objective, using ALS as a representative disease domain and focusing on the interoperability between independently developed clinical data models.

Two complementary harmonization efforts were carried out: (i) mapping between the AnswerALS and PARALS clinical dictionaries, and (ii) alignment of the PARALS dictionary with the GA4GH Beacon v2 data model. Together, these results illustrate both the opportunities and limitations of direct field-level harmonization, and motivate the need for ontology-driven integration within HEREDITARY.

3.2.1 AnswerALS–PARALS Dictionary Harmonization

The manual comparison between the AnswerALS clinical dictionary (approximately 880 variables) and the PARALS dictionary (approximately 100 variables) resulted in the identification of 18 variables that could be mapped through either exact or semantic equivalence, as described in the Methods section. These mappings primarily concern core clinical descriptors such as demographic attributes, high-level disease characteristics, and selected clinical assessments that are explicitly represented in both datasets.

The relatively limited number of one-to-one mappings reflects structural and conceptual differences between the two dictionaries rather than a lack of shared clinical focus. PARALS is a long-standing epidemiological registry with a compact and stable data model, including detailed disease classifications and laboratory measurements—such as blood test parameters—that are not explicitly represented as standalone variables in the AnswerALS dictionary. Conversely, AnswerALS adopts a much more extensive and granular data collection strategy, encompassing a wide range of clinical, molecular, and longitudinal variables that have no direct counterpart in PARALS.

As a result, many clinically related concepts could not be aligned through strict one-to-one field mappings, despite representing overlapping clinical information. This outcome highlights an inherent limitation of direct dictionary-level harmonization when datasets differ significantly in scope, granularity, and modeling assumptions.

The full AnswerALS–PARALS harmonization matrix, including both mapped and unmapped variables, is provided in **Annex 1**. A high-level description of the PARALS fields can be found as part of the deliverables in this project, D3.6 Annex 9 (Chio et al. 2025).

3.2.2 PARALS–Beacon Data Model Alignment

The alignment between the PARALS clinical dictionary and the GA4GH Beacon v2 data model yielded seven Beacon fields to which PARALS variables could be mapped. In contrast to the AnswerALS–PARALS exercise, this mapping follows a many-to-one structure, whereby multiple PARALS variables are aligned to a single Beacon entity.

This result is expected, as the Beacon data model is intentionally minimal and designed primarily for genomic data discovery, rather than comprehensive clinical representation. Consequently, several PARALS variables related to diagnoses, exposures, clinical measurements, and interventions are mapped to broader Beacon fields such as *diseases*, *exposures*, *measurements*, and *interventions*

Table 1. Beacon-PARALS mapping

Beacon Entity	PARALS Concept(s)	Notes
Individuals → id	Participant ID	Exact match
Individuals → age	Age	Exact match
Individuals → sex	Sex	Exact match
Individuals → exposures	Smoking, alcohol	Exposure categories semantically aligned
Individuals → diseases	ALS diagnosis and comorbidities	Many-to-one consolidation into Beacon “diseases” list
Individuals → Measurements	ALSFRS, blood biomarkers	Many-to-one consolidation into Beacon “measurements” list
Individuals → Treatments	Medication	Direct concept match

4 Conclusions and Future Work

This deliverable presents a first pilot of ontology interconversion and data interoperability within the HEREDITARY project, using ALS as a representative disease domain. Through the combined beaconization of genomic data and the semantic harmonization of clinical dictionaries, the pilot demonstrates the feasibility of enabling FAIR, privacy-preserving discovery across heterogeneous datasets that are distributed across institutions and governed by strict access constraints.

The clinical harmonization results show that only a limited number of direct one-to-one mappings (18 variables) could be established between the AnswerALS and PARALS dictionaries. This outcome reflects fundamental differences in dataset scope, granularity, and modeling choices rather than a lack of clinical overlap. PARALS is a compact, long-standing epidemiological registry, while AnswerALS is a highly granular and extensive dataset. These differences limit strict field-level alignment and highlight the intrinsic constraints of dictionary-based harmonization. At the same time, the successful alignment of core clinical concepts confirms that expert-driven semantic mapping can bridge datasets collected under different protocols.

Similarly, the mapping between PARALS and the GA4GH Beacon v2 data model resulted in a small number of Beacon fields to which multiple PARALS variables were aligned. This many-to-one structure reflects the intentionally minimal nature of the Beacon model, which is designed for genomic discovery rather than full clinical representation. Together, these findings motivate the adoption of an ontology-driven approach, such as the HERO ontology, which abstracts clinical meaning away from dataset-specific variables and provides a scalable foundation for cross-cohort integration and automated analysis.

Looking ahead to the full demonstration phase of the project, this pilot lays the groundwork for several key extensions. First, the beaconization effort will be expanded to include the entire UNITO ALS cohort, encompassing both genomic and clinical/phenotypic data. Second, the Beacon instance will be connected to a federated Beacon network, enabling broader discoverability at the European and international level while preserving local data control. Finally, the clinical harmonization work will be refined and extended, with further curation of mappings, mapping of PARALS and AnswerALS to HERO in collaboration with other WP3 teams, and validation against additional datasets within the HEREDITARY ecosystem.

This integrated view clearly positions the pilot as a functional proof-of-concept and outlines the concrete steps leading to the full demonstrator due next year.

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Annexes

Number	Name
Annex 1	HER D3.11 harmonization_matrix.xlsx